

A Report of the Center for English as a Lingua Franca (CELF) for Academic Year 2014-2015

ELFセンター2014-2015レポート

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1. INTRODUCTION

English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) refers to the use of English as a contact language between people who have different first languages, including native English speakers (Jenkins, 2014). “ELF is simultaneously the consequence and the principal language medium of globalizing processes” (Jenkins, Cogo, & Dewey, 2011, p. 303). In connection with Tamagawa University’s goals to enhance education from global perspectives, the Center for English as a Lingua Franca (CELF) at Tamagawa University piloted in 2012 and officially commenced in 2014. The CELF has continually promoted initiatives in raising ELF awareness, improving teaching practices, and researching language education. The objectives of this article are to (1) share CELF’s understanding of ELF; (2) report on student classroom-related activities and teacher professional development initiatives; (3) analyze student and teacher survey results; (4) present TOEIC results; and, (5) discuss future developments in the program.

1. INTRODUCTION

リンガフランカとしての英語とは、第一言語が異なる人（一方が英語話者の場合も含む）との間の接触言語である(Jenkins, 2014)。ELFとは、グローバル化過程における結果と原則的言語手段である(Jenkins, Cogo, & Dewey, 2011, p. 303)。玉川大学のグローバル化教育促進という目標に伴い、玉川大学ELFプログラムは2012年に試験的に開始され、2014年に正式にセンターが設立された。ELFセンターでは、ELFに対する認知度を上げることに力を入れると共に、実践的教育を改善し、言語教育に対する研究も行っている。本稿では、(1) ELFセンターの考えるELF、(2) 学生の教室内活動と教員のプロフェッショナル開発に関するレポート、(3) 学生と教員のアンケート結果分析、(4) TOEICの結果、(5) 今後のプログラムの発展について述べる。

2. TAMAGAWA UNIVERSITY'S RESPONSE TO GLOBALIZATION

Zenjin education is Tamagawa University's philosophy that aims to integrate the values of society and culture harmoniously into individual propensities. Tamagawa students are encouraged to learn not only through instruction but also autonomously, allowing them to acquire the skills and tools necessary in developing a broad awareness of the globalization process. Globalization involves increasing opportunities for contact in global markets and services and participation in international events and activities where English plays a central role as the common language linking people with different first languages. It is, thus, essential for people in the 21st century to acquire communication abilities in English in its use as a common international language (Seargeant, 2009). In response to global trends and in conjunction with preparations for the 2020 Tokyo Olympics, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT) has been incrementally promoting educational reform with full-scale development of new English language education curricula in Japan (MEXT, 2014). The globalization of English has become a key aspect in the strategic response to globalization of many universities (Jenkins, 2014). The establishment of the CELF is a significant part of Tamagawa University's response to the demands placed on institutions of higher learning by globalization processes.

3. CENTER FOR ENGLISH AS A LINGUA FRANCA, FROM 2012 TO PRESENT

In 2012, the English as a Lingua Franca (ELF) program offered classes to 436 students in the College of Business Administration and College of Humanities. In the following year, students from the College of Tourism & Hospitality Management, the College of Liberal Arts, and the High School Bridging Program joined, and the number of students increased to 1,117. With the establishment of the CELF in 2014, enrollment rose to 1,795 with students from the College of Arts enrolling in the program. At the time of writing, students in the Colleges of Education, Engineering and Agriculture are expected to enroll in 2015 bringing student numbers to 2,472 (See Table 1).

Table 1

Cumulative enrollment of the CELF each year

College	Department	2012	2013	2014	2015
Business Admin.	-International Mngmt.	171	321	375	347
	-Tourism & Hospitality Management	108	100	97	-
Humanities	-Comparative Cultures	157	320	408	295
	-Human Science	-	-	87	104
Tourism & Hospitality	Tourism & Hospitality Management	-	108	197	225
Arts & Sciences	Liberal Arts	-	180	338	208

Arts	-Performing Arts	-	-	139	159
	-Media Design	-	-	96	118
Engineering	-Intelligent Mechanical Systems	-	40 (elective)	14 (elective)	78
	-Software Science	-	-	-	78
	- Management Science	-	-	-	78
	- Engineering Design	-	-	-	78
Education	-Education	-	-	-	326
	-Early Childhood Care & Development (2016 entry)	-	-	-	-
Agriculture	-Bioenvironmental Systems	-	-	-	111
	-Biosource Engineering	-	-	-	111
	-Life Science	-	-	-	111
High School	Bridging Program	-	48	44	45
TOTALS		436	1,117	1,795	2,472

The hiring practices of teachers for the ELF program are based on two criteria: teaching experience and academic achievements. There is no requirement for CELF teachers to be native speakers of English. All faculty members speak English as their first or second language and have a master or doctoral degree in TESOL, Applied Linguistics, Education, or a related field in the Social Sciences, with the majority of teachers having teaching experience at the tertiary level in Japan. The program's teachers are of diverse backgrounds and nationalities. The seven full-time faculty members and 19 part-time teachers in 2013 grew to nine full-time faculty and 25 part-time instructors in 2014, including teachers from Australia, Canada, England, India, Japan, New Zealand, Northern Ireland, South Korea, The Philippines, The United States and Ukraine. The CELF's multi-lingual teachers are encouraged to integrate language awareness in their lessons and expose their students to different kinds of Englishes.

The CELF offers classes in four levels from elementary to intermediate each semester. The TOEIC Bridge is used to assess the proficiency of all incoming first-year students at the beginning of the semester in order to place them in the appropriate ELF level. CELF students meet 200 minutes every week for 15 weeks for 50 hours of study in class each semester, and are required to study eight hours outside the classroom each week. There are also intensive sessions during the summer and winter breaks for students who have matriculated since 2013 who want to meet their graduation requirements or improve their Grade Point Average (GPA). Students take the TOEIC IP test at the end of each semester and session. The students are evaluated based on the following five components: Reading Comprehension 20%, Listening and Speaking Assessment 20%, Process Writing Assessment 20%, TOEIC IP Scores 20%, Class Work, Participation and Homework 20%. English is used as the main medium of

communication in all classes, and the use of any other linguistic resource, such as Japanese, is compatible with ELF-aware teaching.

4. CELF's UNDERSTANDING OF ENGLISH AS A LINGUA FRANCA

4.1 Understanding English as a Lingua Franca

English is now the most widely used means of international and intercultural communication. Although most uses of English occur away from L1 settings (Cogo & Dewey, 2006), it is L1 versions of English which are regarded as prestigious (Seidlhofer, 2011). Such native varieties, however, developed to meet the communicative needs of particular societies, have "restricted relevance" for the majority of English users, whose needs and reasons for using English are different from those of native speakers (Seidlhofer, 2011, p. 148). Native speakers are likely to be in the minority in "de-territorialised speech events" across the world and their English "will therefore be less and less likely to constitute the only linguistic reference norm" (Seidlhofer, 2014).

Despite significant changes in the use and users of the language, there is an "uncritical tendency ... to persist in traditional ways of thinking about English" (Jenkins 2014, p. 18). It is thought that the only 'acceptable' English communication is linguistically 'correct' English (Seidlhofer, 2011). The assumption that non-native varieties are deficient is challenged by Widdowson (2012b), who argues that the competence of non-native ELF users cannot correspond with the competence of native speakers. Native speakers, he points out, experience English through primary socialization, "whereby language, culture and social identity are naturally and inseparably connected" (2012b, p. 18). Non-native speakers, he goes on to say, experience English through secondary socialization, separated from these inherent connections. He elsewhere notes that most learners of English will "never even approximate" native norms (Widdowson, 2014). Although native English models are valuable, particularly for learners who will communicate with native speakers, native proficiency is neither a realistic goal nor an achievable one for millions of learners (Björkman, 2013).

English which does not conform to native norms is used for effective communication in lingua franca situations across the world. English need not necessarily be connected to particular countries or ethnicities (Vikor, 2004, p. 329 as cited in Seidlhofer, 2011). It can be used for functionally appropriate, strategic and effective communication in any local community (Seidlhofer, 2011). English can be thought of as belonging to everyone who uses it. Language ownership is equated by Brumfit (2001, p. 116) with "the power to adapt and change" a language.

Rather than being defined according to its form as compared with native norms, ELF is defined by its function in intercultural communication (Hülmbauer, Böhringer, & Seidlhofer, 2008). ELF communication has been characterized as diverse, flexible and creative by Kaur (2014), who notes the supportive and cooperative nature of ELF interactions, as well as the use of strategies for effective communication, such as paraphrasing, checking or requesting clarification, confirming, signaling (non-) understanding, and repetition.

In 2011, Jenkins et al. observed that, with the exception of Walker's (2010) ELF-oriented pronunciation handbook for teachers, and the final chapter of Understanding

English as a Lingua Franca (Seidlhofer, 2011), there had been little discussion of the possibilities of ELF-informed pedagogy, and little consideration of measures for teachers to consider. Investigations into pedagogical implications were encouraged through the special focus on pedagogical perspectives at the Seventh International Conference of English as a Lingua Franca in September 2014.

4.2 Classroom Application of ELF Principles

Rather than prescribing teaching practices, ELF researchers are responsible for making research findings accessible to teachers who are then enabled to “reconsider their beliefs and practices and make informed decisions about the significance of ELF for their own individual teaching contexts” (Jenkins et al., 2011, p. 306). Bjorkman (2013) recognizes the significance of accuracy in language, but emphasizes that communication is more important. She suggests that teachers raise awareness of English usage in the world as well as providing pertinent models and attainable goals. Bjorkman suggests a range of measures for teachers to consider. She firstly advises prioritizing comprehensibility in language teaching by exposing learners to a wide range of English, by reducing the ‘nativespeakerist’ element in some teaching materials, and by having models which can be applied to a variety of communicative goals. Bjorkman next suggests modifying course materials, by including listening comprehension materials with a variety of accents, by including cases of disturbance which provide examples of negotiation of meaning and use of communicative strategies, and by including authentic recordings from which students can test listening comprehension. She also advocates including pragmatic strategies in listening and speaking materials. Bjorkman’s final recommendation is to change speaking testing so it is clear that non-native accents are not a barrier to achievement of the highest grades. She suggests that not only monologic speech should be tested but also dialogic speech, so that a learner’s ability to negotiate meaning and to communicate are effectively evaluated.

If being proficient in English means being able to communicate effectively with people from various speech communities throughout the world, there is a sense in which “the argument becomes irrelevant whether local standards or inner-circle standards matter” (Canagarajah, 2006, p. 233). Canagarajah believes we need the ability to negotiate English varieties in outer and expanding communities as well as varieties in inner circle countries. Jenkins agrees, noting that Inner Circle speakers do not set the linguistic agenda in ELF communication, and arguing that “no matter which circle of use we come from...we all need to make adjustments to our local English variety for the benefit of our interlocutors when we take part in lingua franca English communication” (2009, p. 201).

5. CELF STUDENTS’ CLASSROOM-RELATED ACTIVITIES

Beyond the learning engagement found in regular classroom activities, CELF students may encounter various cultural and language oriented learning experiences. The CELF Tutor Service provides students with frequently available on-campus contact with tutors who are of various language and cultural backgrounds. During each week of the semester students may sign up to meet with a tutor, or a teacher can refer a student to visit a tutor for learning support. In 2014, there were 75 tutor sessions in spring semester and 114 tutor sessions

in autumn semester offered weekly, four days a week. Tutor sessions are fifteen minutes in duration, and students may attend up to four sessions per week. Online attendance logs kept by each tutor indicate that a total of 700 tutor consultations took place during the fall semester of 2014. Attendance log data revealed that students most frequently requested tutor assistance for Writing (214 sessions), Listening and Speaking (180 sessions), Other (149 sessions), and TOEIC related (49 sessions). Trends in student selections for tutor assistance are being closely followed in order to better serve the needs of the users of this service. Additionally, throughout the academic year students in some classes enjoy classroom visits from groups of international university students visiting Japan on study tours. In the past year students from Evergreen College (USA) and Guam University visited CELF classes. It is an important objective of the CELF to provide quality learning engagement opportunities both inside and outside of the ELF classroom.

6. CELF TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Previous CELF research has shown that it is the teachers, their personal beliefs and principles, who largely determine the success of a language program (Cote, Milliner, McBride, Imai, & Ogane, 2014). Consequently, the CELF endeavors to ensure that its teachers have a range of avenues for professional development and teaching support open to them throughout the academic year. Professional development is offered to the CELF teaching staff in the form of opportunities to participate in teacher orientations and ELF related workshops. The university's BlackBoard Course Management System is an online learning environment that provides an important avenue for teachers to develop professionally. Using the BlackBoard system, the CELF has created a space for ELF and Extensive Reading guidelines, a teacher's blog for discussions about teaching and learning, as well as a "drop box" for the sharing of teaching ideas which all contribute to a platform for the support of teacher development and practices (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1
Language awareness page inside the CELF teacher resources page

Additional access to professional development is provided in the form of a teacher’s research forum, where teachers are invited to share their research and teaching ideas, and all teachers are invited to contribute articles for publication in The Center for English as a Lingua Franca Journal and collaborative journal issues with The Journal of Saitama City Educators. An important goal of our ongoing professional discourse and support through these various professional development initiatives is to achieve a greater awareness among CELF teachers of ELF-related teaching concepts and their application in ELF-oriented classroom environments.

7. STUDENT SURVEY RESULTS

At the end of both spring and fall semesters the CELF conducts an online student questionnaire via SurveyMonkey < www.surveymonkey.com >. The questionnaire is bilingual, that is English and Japanese, and it is expected to gauge student perceptions of the ELF curriculum and their learning experiences. This year’s set of questions compared to last year’s, focused more on ELF awareness and perceptions. Students are able to respond to the open-ended questionnaire items in English or Japanese and the Japanese responses were translated into English for this report. The response rates for spring and fall semesters were 76% and 86% respectively.

7.1 Student Perceptions of the ELF Program

As summarised in Table 2, students appear to have a positive perception of the ELF program. A total of 88% in the spring and 84% of students in the fall either strongly agreed or agreed that what they learned in the class was worthwhile, and 76% and 72% respectively either agreed or strongly agreed that they were satisfied with the ELF program. Students’ responses to items relating to their experiences inside the ELF classroom were also positive. Close to 80% of students in both semesters either strongly agreed or agreed that the classes were interesting and that they enjoyed the atmosphere of their ELF classes.

These positive student perceptions were also reinforced when students commented on the ELF program. A student noted, *“The practical focus on English was very helpful for me. I didn’t like studying English before, but now I do. As a result, I hope that this ELF program isn’t changed.”* Another student stated, *“The program helped me develop my knowledge about the practical application of English.”*

Table 2
Student perceptions of the ELF classes and curriculum

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
What I learned in the ELF program was worthwhile. (spring)	539 42%	591 46%	112 9%	27 2%	10 1%
What I learned in the ELF program was worthwhile. (fall)	457 38%	551 46%	123 10%	46 4%	11 1%

I am satisfied with the ELF program. (spring)	385 30%	588 46%	219 17%	73 6%	14 1%
I am satisfied with the ELF program. (fall)	341 29%	507 43%	228 19%	85 7%	27 2%
The ELF class was interesting. (spring)	530 41%	514 40%	164 13%	49 4%	22 2%
The ELF class was interesting. (fall)	457 39%	450 38%	182 15%	71 6%	28 2%
I enjoyed the atmosphere of this class. (spring)	570 44%	455 36%	195 15%	47 4%	12 1%
I enjoyed the atmosphere of this class. (fall)	497 42%	441 37%	183 16%	51 4%	16 1%

7.2 Student Responses to ELF Related Questionnaire Items

To continue previous research on student perceptions of ELF, and in an effort to inform teachers about how students respond to ELF-related information, six Likert items were added to the surveys. The results are summarized in Table 3. Student responses to these items did not appear to have changed between spring and fall semesters. A large majority (88% in spring and 85% in fall) either agreed or strongly agreed with the practical focus of the classes and 84% of students in both semesters were in agreement that English does not belong only to native speakers and that it can be their language too. The ELF-related question that attracted the lowest level of student agreement was, "The ELF classes helped me to initiate conversations and continue them in English." About half (42% in the spring and 58% in the fall) agreed with this statement. This feedback suggests that teachers may need to invest more time in speaking and/or fluency activities and consider promoting use of the tutor service as a chance for students to practice their conversation skills outside of class.

Table 3

Summary of student responses to the ELF-specific questionnaire items

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I agree with the practical focus on English in ELF classes. (spring)	506 40%	619 48%	135 11%	15 1%	4 <1%
I agree with the practical focus on English in ELF classes. (fall)	447 38%	565 47%	141 12%	34 3%	4 <1%
The ELF classes helped me to initiate conversations and continue them in English. (spring)	-	535 42%	522 41%	177 14%	5 3%
The ELF classes helped me to initiate conversations and continue them in English. (fall)	191 16%	496 42%	339 28%	126 11%	39 3%

I don't think English belongs to native speakers. It can be my language too. (spring)	459 36%	615 48%	178 14%	22 2%	5 <1%
I don't think English belongs to native speakers. It can be my language too. (fall)	422 36%	581 49%	154 13%	26 2%	8 <1%
I think I will use English with non-native speakers in the future. (spring)	476 37%	553 43%	204 16%	35 3%	11 1%
I think I will use English with non-native speakers in the future. (fall)	469 39%	484 41%	185 16%	44 4%	9 <1%
English is not only a language which native speakers use, but a language that I may construct/modify for my communicative purposes. (spring)	351 27%	668 52%	225 18%	32 2%	3 <1%
English is not only a language which native speakers use, but a language that I may construct/modify for my communicative purposes. (fall)	328 28%	631 53%	195 16%	32 3%	5 <1%
When learning English, I want to aim towards a native speaker model of English. (spring)	483 38%	510 40%	228 18%	44 3%	14 1%
When using English, as long as my English is internationally intelligible, I don't have to be like a native speaker. (fall)	191 16%	496 42%	339 28%	126 11%	39 3%

Note: *Due to a formatting error in the electronic survey, students were unable to choose the strongly agree option when responding to the statement, "The ELF classes helped me to initiate conversations and continue them in English" in the spring semester survey.

** Percentages have been rounded to remove decimal places.

Students generally appear to have embraced ELF, yet most students still appear to want to target native models. Respondents either strongly agreed (38%) or agreed (40%) with the statement "When learning English, I want to aim towards a native speaker model of English." This statement was rephrased for the fall questionnaire, as "When using English, as long as my English is internationally intelligible, I don't have to be like a native speaker." This time, a total of 58% students were in agreement. This result may suggest a change in values for some students after they experienced ELF classes, however, the 164 (14%) respondents in disagreement and a further 339 (28%) choosing neutral illustrates that some students

may still hold native speaker benchmarks. It has been observed by Suzuki (2011) that these perceptions may have been influenced by previous educational experiences, or popular ideologies in Japan (Harris, 2012). There is a long-held assumption that native speaker competence should be a primary teaching and learning objective in English language education (McKay, 2002; Seidlhofer, 2011; Tanaka & Ogane, 2011; Widdowson, 2012a). Consequently, ELF users are characterized as incompetent when their performance does not conform to standard native speaker norms (Widdowson, 2012b). The CELF is planning to consider this issue more deeply as it reviews learning support materials and considers a reconfiguration of speaking assessments used in the ELF program.

One aspect of a program such as ours is that students do not often have contact with speakers of other first languages. There were a total of 52 student comments relating to this theme in the spring survey and 26 in the fall. Some examples of student comments included: (1) *"I would like more opportunities to speak in English"*; and (2) *"I would like more opportunities to study abroad and to interact with native speakers."* During spring semester some classes were visited by students from the University of Guam. One Japanese student noted, *"When the Guam students came to class, it was the best learning experience for me. I would like to have experiences like this at least once a week."* Unfortunately, there are no exchange students studying at Tamagawa University, and as a result, there are few opportunities on campus for students to communicate with other English speakers outside class time. A student noted, *"There are many teachers from other country in Tamagawa University, so I want to talk with many teachers from many countries."* This comment suggests that the CELF needs to consider how it can leverage its most valuable ELF asset, its teachers, to increase student engagement using ELF. The ELF tutor service represents one construct where students can engage using ELF. As stated earlier more students are using the service and some students recognized the benefits of this service when they made comments about the ELF program. For example, (1) *"It was great being able to listen to a variety of teachers."*; and, (2) *"It's nice how we can talk with a variety of teachers in the tutor service. I also learned that it was easier to communicate with some teachers compared to others."* The CELF will continue to compare these results with results from future student questionnaires to achieve a deeper understanding about student perceptions of the ELF program and ELF-related issues, and to make decisions on how the program can be refined.

8. CELF TEACHER SURVEY RESULTS

Results from the teacher questionnaire conducted in the spring and fall semesters of 2014 were collated via SurveyMonkey < www.surveymonkey.com > and analyzed in order to understand teacher perceptions of the ELF program and ELF usage. The response rate was 53% (19 out of a total of 34 teachers) in the spring and 88 % (30 out of 34) in the fall. The results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

Teacher perceptions of the ELF classes and curriculum

Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
It is all right if my students don't become like native English speakers as long as they can communicate effectively. (spring)	16 85%	3 15%	-	-	-
I think my students should have the freedom not to follow native speaker models. (spring)	10 53%	4 22%	3 15%	2 10%	-
Students' effective communication is more important than strict conformity to native speaker norms. (fall)	18 86%	2 9%	1 5%	-	-
I would like to spend less time in class on the finer points of normative models of English and more on attainable forms of English. (spring)	8 43%	7 37%	3 15%	1 5%	-
I would like to spend less time in class on the finer points of normative models of English and more on attainable forms of English. (fall)	7 33%	8 38%	6 29%	-	-
I believe the use of the students' native language in the classroom can be a pragmatic resource. (spring)	7 37%	9 48%	2 10%	1 5%	-
I believe the use of the students' native language in the classroom can be a pragmatic resource. (fall)	7 33%	10 47%	2 10%	2 10%	-
I think ELF is suitable in a Japanese context. (spring)	11 58%	5 27%	2 10%	1 5%	-
I think ELF is suitable in a Japanese context. (fall)	9 42%	7 33%	5 24%	-	-
The ELF classes have helped my students initiate conversations and continue them in English. (spring)	7 37%	8 43%	3 15%	1 5%	-
The ELF classes have helped my students initiate conversations and continue them in English. (fall)	4 19%	14 67%	2 9%	-	1 5%

Note: *Percentages have been rounded to remove decimal places.

This questionnaire explored teacher perceptions of the ELF classes and curriculum, providing evidence of a strong degree of teacher support for the curriculum and for the application of ELF principles in classroom learning. In relation to the belief that it is alright if their students do not become like native speakers as long as they can communicate effectively, there was agreement or strong agreement from 100% of the teachers. In the spring questionnaire, a majority, 75% of the teachers, were in agreement that their students should have the freedom not to follow native speaker models. In the fall questionnaire this item was modified to, "Students' effective communication is more important than strict conformity to native speaker norms." Teacher responses to this item attracted the highest rate of agreement (85%). These results might suggest that teachers are considering some of the information relating to ELF principles that is being shared between CELF faculty. Some teachers, however, may not be entirely convinced that ELF is suitable for the tertiary Japanese context. A total of 85% of the CELF teachers agreed or strongly agreed that "ELF is suitable in the Japanese context" in spring, and 75% agreed or strongly agreed in the fall. The fact that a quarter of respondents in the fall chose neither to agree nor disagree with the suitability of ELF may suggest that some teachers are actively considering the appropriateness of ELF principles.

Teacher responses to the statement, "The ELF classes have helped my students initiate conversations and continue them in English" somewhat contradicted student perceptions. A total of 85% of teachers in the fall agreed or strongly agreed with this statement. Whereas 339 students (28%) were neutral and 165 (14%) disagreed with the statement "The ELF classes helped me to initiate conversations and continue them in English." This misalignment suggests that more work needs to be done to investigate student and teacher benchmarks for a successful conversation and whether one is able to continue conversations over a duration of time.

Evidence of teacher awareness concerning ELF-related teaching practices can be found in comments offered by the spring questionnaire respondents. In regard to the issue of learner errors one teacher commented, "*Japanese students are very conscious of mistakes, particularly in grammar.*" Another teacher commented on learner 'errors' in connection with class time, stating, "*I realize I have used class time unproductively in the past by correcting writing errors which students would not be expected to remember or to master in the time available.*" Additionally, in relation to the evaluation of listening and speaking assessment, the following perspective was offered by a teacher: "*I reflected from an ELF perspective on the way I scored the listening and speaking test, and I realized how insignificant it was to focus too much on grammatical errors.*" This teacher's perception of classroom teaching and learning practices highlights the importance of facilitating alignment of ELF principles with components of the curriculum. Results from this questionnaire indicate that the majority of the program's teachers are in agreement with practicing ELF-informed teaching and that the teachers from various backgrounds find the ELF program satisfactory and meaningful.

9. OVERVIEW OF TOEIC RESULTS

The Test of English for International Communication (TOEIC) is the most widely accepted English test in Japan and in a majority of cases, a TOEIC score is required on job applications

(Chujo & Oghigian, 2009) and for giving promotions (Tsuji & Tsuji, 2006). The TOEIC Listening and Reading Test is administered twice a year during the ELF Program; once in the spring term and once in the fall term, and these results make up one component of the final ELF course assessment. For the first time this year, the TOEIC Speaking and Writing Test was offered to those students interested in determining their English skills as measured by this speaking and writing proficiency test. The table below shows the average 2014 spring and fall listening and reading test results for all participating colleges and departments.

Table 5
Average 2014 Listening & Reading TOEIC IP test scores for each of the participating colleges and departments

College	Department	Spring TOEIC IP	Fall TOEIC IP
Humanities	Comparative Cultures	391.4	407.9
	Human Sciences	300	375
Arts & Sciences	Liberal Arts	346.6	344.1
Business Administration	International Management	342.6	345.8
	Tourism & Hospitality Management	387.7	403.3
Arts	Performing Arts	315.5	327.5
	Media Design	312.3	321
Tourism & Hospitality Management	Tourism & Hospitality Management	439.7	456.8

10. CONCLUSION & CELF MOVING FORWARD

The globally widespread use of English for communication involving non-native English speakers has provoked a questioning of traditional approaches to the teaching and learning of the language. ELF suggests a reorganizing of pedagogical priorities, and a focus on how learners can most effectively use the language they already know as well as practicing the communication processes that are most useful for them. The CELF is Tamagawa University's response to such globalization processes as the ELF phenomenon. Our research and discussions on ELF will continue as we endeavor to develop teaching and learning practices in which are most beneficial for our students, bearing in mind the importance of Tamagawa University's Zenjin educational philosophy.

Teacher knowledge is crucial to effective classroom practice. Professional development activities at CELF not only encourage our teachers to exchange ideas on research and teaching practices, but also provide opportunities to help raise ELF awareness and understanding among the faculty. Professional development opportunities include presenting at the CELF Forum and contributing to the CELF Journal. Teachers may also

participate in CELF workshops and use the BlackBoard for sharing teaching resources. CELF initiatives in professional development will continue and be strengthened.

Our survey results show that many CELF students appear to be targeting native speaker proficiency. The majority of CELF teachers, on the other hand, appear to believe that the students need not become like native speakers as long as they can communicate effectively. A majority of teachers also appear to believe that students should have the freedom not to follow native speaker models. Survey feedback also indicates that while some CELF students want more listening and speaking opportunities, most teachers believe they are helping them in initiating and continuing conversations. It is hoped that the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of our teachers may help students become more aware of the different usages of English as they learn together not only in class but also during tutor sessions. We hope to help prepare them to become adept speakers in ELF contexts which are manifestations of the globalization process.

As the CELF moves to become a campus-wide enterprise in 2015, we continue our work to develop guidelines for an ELF-oriented pedagogy. Immediate plans are to evaluate the teaching materials and speaking assessments used in our program. Our goal for CELF is to raise an awareness of language in our students, an awareness of language in use which involves the negotiation and accommodation of linguistic form and meaning.

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